

State Estimation of Cylindrical Lithium-Ion Batteries Using Strain Gages

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Abstract

Lithium-Ion batteries (LIB) are nowadays used in various applications, ranging from smartphones to power tools and electric vehicles. In all these applications, a battery management system (BMS) determines the state of charge (SOC) and the state of health (SOH) of the LIB by measuring the cell voltages, the current and the temperature of the cells. The general state (SOX) of a LIB is not only represented by these values but also by its mechanical properties that are closely linked to the electrochemical characteristics. During charging and discharging lithium-ions intercalate and de-intercalate in the active materials of a LIB leading to a change in several mechanical properties. Besides the Young's modulus, Poisson ratio and the density, also the thickness of the electrodes changes [1]. In recent years, research has significantly intensified to better understand these changes, to enhance the SOX estimation, and to identify additional conditions that are difficult to detect solely through the measurements provided by the BMS. To achieve this, various types of sensors, such as piezoelectric transducers, force/pressure sensors, and strain gages, are employed to monitor these mechanical changes.

In this work strain gages are mounted on cylindrical cells to measure surface strain variations on the housing caused by changes in thickness of the active materials during cycling. While thickness changes are existent in both the anode and cathode active material, they are more pronounced in the anode [1]. Therefore, during charging the overall volume of the jelly roll increases and subsequently presses against the cell housing. This leads to an increase in the surface strain measured by the strain gage. During discharging the jelly roll shrinks and the opposite effect can be measured. To the authors knowledge this is the first work that implements strain measurements on three different cylindrical cell types and correlates the measured strain with the electrical properties. In Figure 1 the voltages and the corresponding strain measurement results of three different cells during cycling with 0.1C (subplot a,b) and 0.15C

(subplot c) can be seen. While for the cells Samsung 18650 35E (subplot b) and the BAK 4695 (subplot c) the strain behaves like previously stated, the strain measurement shows an inverse behaviour for the Samsung 18650 29E (subplot a). Only on one position close to the negative tab, an increase in strain during charging and a decrease in strain during discharging could be measured. To investigate this position dependency and the different behaviours in strain, an extensive postmortem analysis of all three cells was conducted. Besides opening the cells to investigate the internal structures, an analysis of the composition from the anode and cathode active materials was as well performed. The findings showed that the internal structure of both Samsung 18650 cells is identical but that the Samsung 35E has a silicon doped anode. Due to the higher volumetric change of silicon [1], the positioning of the strain gage does not influence the measurement result on the silicon containing cylindrical cell. For the non-silicon containing cell this circumstance leads to a strong variation and even an inverse behaviour in the measured strain. The strong dependency of the strain on the silicon content of the anode active material has been comprehensively demonstrated in this work for the first time. These findings are of significant importance if strain gages are used to improve the SOX estimation of a LIB. Additionally, the strain evolution during cycling was measured on the novel cell format of 46950. The results showed that due to the general higher volume of the cell, measurements with strain gages profit due to the increased volumetric changes, leading to overall higher strain values.

Additionally, abusive overcharging tests were conducted on all three cell types while the strain on the cells surface was measured. The results of these tests and the benefits compared to regular temperature sensors are discussed. An outlook on how strain gages can be used to enhance not only the estimation of SOC and SOH but also improve the state determination during safety critical events is given.

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[1] A. Mukhopadhyay and B. W. Sheldon, "Deformation and stress in electrode materials for Li-ion batteries," *Progress in Materials Science*, vol. 63, pp. 58–116, Jun. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.pmatsci.2014.02.001.